

EVALUATION OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF BERRY FRUITS MARKETED IN ALBANIA

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ABSTRACT

Berry fruits are considered essential components of a healthy diet, playing an important role in human nutrition, and recently the interest on them by food scientist and consumers is growing. This study undertake to evaluate physico-chemical parameters of berry fruits blueberry (*Vaccinium spp.*), blackberry (*Rubus spp.*), raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*) and strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa*), which were marketed in Albania. Fruits were collected randomly in Tirana markets, and were evaluated for fruits dimensions, total dry matter (D.M.), total soluble solids (TSS), total titratable acidity (TTA), pH, total ash, vitamin C, and colour for L*, a* and b*. Determined parameters resulted: fruit length 10.80-45.92 mm and width 13.03-35.38, D.M. 20.27-43.4 g/100 g f.w., g/100 g f.w., TSS 9-15 °Brix, TTA 3.74-6.73 g/100 g of sample fresh weight (f.w.), pH 3.1-3.7, total ash 0.31-0.71 g/100 g f.w., L* 17.05-30.26, a* 1.58-18.93, and b* from -4.01 to 6.49, vitamin C ranged 10.6-48.8 mg/100 g f.w. From comparison between fruits blackberry resulted with the highest content of D.M., ash, pH, and with the lowest TTA, strawberry resulted with the highest vitamin C content and blueberry with the highest TSS, whereas L* value was higher in blueberry and lower in blackberry, had the highest a* and b* values in raspberry, and the lowest in blueberry. Variation were noted for TTA, TSS and vitamin C, whereas no significant differences were noted for other determined physico-chemical parameters. Future studies may be focused on investigation of total polyphenol content and antioxidant potential of these fruits.

Key words: blueberry; blackberry; raspberry; strawberry; physico-chemical parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Berries have been recognized to play an important role in human nutrition providing health-benefits (Manganaris et al., 2013).

Albania is placed in the Mediterranean Basin, offering enormous opportunities to grow many fruit crops, which have found spontaneous and wild forms of blackberries, raspberries (*Rubus*), strawberries (*Fragaria*) and vacciniums, and are part of a natural ecosystems (Kullaj et al. 2012).

They are consumed both as fresh fruit and are processed to form value-added products such as juice, puree, concentrate and frozen berries beverages, ice cream, yogurt, milkshakes, jams, jellies, spreads, syrups, wines, teas, and dairy products (Curi et al., 2016; Kadivec et al., 2013).

This study undertake to evaluate physico-chemical parameters of berry fruits blueberry (*Vaccinium spp.*), blackberry (*Rubus spp.*), raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*) and strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa*), which were marketed in Albania.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Berry fruits selected for this study blueberry (*Vaccinium* spp.), blackberry (*Rubus* spp.), red raspberry (*Rubus idaeus*), and strawberry (*Fragaria ananassa*). Fruits were randomly collected in 2021 in Tirana markets, Albania, and were transported immediately to the laboratory. Prior analyzation a pre-selection was done based on fruits maturity, shape, size, and color.

Fifty berry fruits of each cultivar was individually weighed and measured for the principal dimensions. For determination of dry matter was weighed exactly 5 g of the well-homogenized sample into a pre-dried and tarred container and was placed the container in the moisture analyzer (model OHAUS) at $105 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and let it dry, and results were expressed as g/100 g of sample in fresh basis. Total soluble solids (TSS) was measured at 20°C using the ABBE refractometer and results were expressed in °Brix. Total titratable acidity (TTA) was determined by potentiometric method for which the titration with a standard alkali solution (0.1N NaOH) (in the presence of 0.3 mL phenolphthalein) was performed until its pH reached 8.1 and results were expressed in g citric acid per 100 g of sample f.w. Also, was determined the ratio of TSS/TTA. pH was measured, after the pH-meter was standardized using standard buffers with pH 4 and 7. For total ash content determination was weighted 5 gm (approximately 0.001 g) test sample into a previously dried and tarred crochet and incinerated in a muffle furnace at a temperature of $525 \pm 25^\circ\text{C}$, and results were calculated g/100 g of sample f.w. The surface color of the berry fruits was measured using a portable colorimeter (model NH310) to determine L* (lightness or darkness), a* (redness or greenness) and b* (yellowness or blueness) values. The ascorbic acid content was determined using the method of 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol, as described by AOAC (2000).

The analyzes were performed at least in three replications, and were calculated as Mean values, \pm standard deviation.

Figure 1. Berry fruits of the study: a) blueberry, b) blackberry, c) red raspberry, and d) strawberry

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the study results, the berry fruits are small fruits with a weight per fruit 1.08-25.10 g, length 10.80-45.92 mm, width 13.03-35.38 mm and fruit shape index 0.83-1.3 (Table 1), among them blueberry is the smallest and strawberry the biggest. Such fruits are

characterized by soft flesh that lacks a peel or inner core, making them highly perishable (Bates, et al., 2001).

Table 1. Weight, dimensions and fruit shape index of berry fruits (expressed as Mean values \pm SD)

Fruits	Weight per fruit	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Fruit shape index
blueberry	1.08 \pm 0.39	10.80 \pm 0.999	13.03 \pm 1.69	0.83 \pm 1.34
blackberry	4.78 \pm 0.27	19.32 \pm 1.84	17.79 \pm 1.30	1.09 \pm 1.09
raspberry	5.27 \pm 0.45	23.22 \pm 1.72	20.72 \pm 1.75	1.12 \pm 0.982
strawberry	25.10 \pm 0.89	45.92 \pm 6.93	35.38 \pm 3.76	1.3 \pm 5.35

Fruit color is a key component of fruit quality (García-Viguera et al., 1998). Colors form the color spectrum and usually include red, reddish-purple, purple, blue-purple, blue, blue-green, green, yellow-green, yellow, and orange. Light is the difference between brightness and darkness, or the amount of white or black present in a color. The value range of L* (light) is from 0 = black to 100 = white, the range a* is negative for green to positive for red and the values b* are negative for blue and positive for yellow (Palonena and Weber 2019). The coloration is generally the first characteristic observed in fresh foods, and very often predetermines the consumer expectation in relation to the flavor and quality.

Figure 2. The color parameters of the berry fruits determined using CIE L* a*, b*

The color parameters of the samples were determined using CIE L* a*, b*, and the values resulted respectively 17.05-30.26; 1.58-18.93 and -4.01 to 6.49 (Figure 2). Among the red fruits, the blueberry had the highest L* value (30.26), and the lowest blackberry (17.05). Raspberry resulted with a higher positive value of a* (18.93) indicating that they are redder in the skin, and with a lower value resulted blueberry (1.58). Raspberry had the higher positive value b* (6.49), and with lower values resulted blueberry (-4.01).

Size, color, and shape, are considered important for external appearance of fruits, and for consumers. Color is a key parameter of post-harvest quality for red fruits and value L*, a*, b* are highly influenced by genotype, storage temperature and storage duration. In addition, physical factors, such as color and its uniformity, are parameters that directly define the quality of the fruits, because it is considered to interfere with features, such as flavor and intensity (Moreno and Deaquiz, 2016).

During the ripening process, which is a complex process, fruit undergoes continuous physicochemical changes that affect acceptability, quality, and storage time (Ayala et al., 2013) often associated with an increase in soluble solids, total sugars, total ascorbic acid, pH, and a decrease in acidity among others (Moreno and Deaquiz, 2016).

Figure 3. Dry matter of berry fruits

Dry matter of berry fruits resulted 20.27-43.4 g/100 g of sample f.w. (Figure 3), where blackberry had the higher content (43.4 g/100 g) and blueberry the lowest content (20.27 g/100 g). Dry matter for berry fruits in this study resulted higher than the study of Françoiso et al. (2008), Souza et al. (2014) and similar to the study of Moraes et al. (2007).

Figure 4. Total soluble solids, total titratable acidity, pH and TSS/TTA values of berry fruits

The soluble solids content is an important characteristic for products that are sold fresh, since consumers have a preference for sweeter fruits (Mahmood et al., 2012; Silva et al., 2002). The total soluble solids content of all the samples showed considerable differences as resulted 9-15°Brix (Figure 4), where highest content had blackberry, no significant differences existed among blueberry, raspberry and strawberry. Total soluble solids is affected by cultivar and harvest maturity, and berries should be harvested at a near full ripe stage to retain the sweetness and appropriate flavor as the soluble solids content of berries remain unchanged post harvesting (Mitcham, 2007).

Acidity is one of the criteria that affect the classification of fruit. Total titratable acidity of all samples differed from one another and the results were higher than those reported by Moura et al. (2011) and Hirsch et al. (2012).

The measured physico-chemical properties corresponded very well, i.e., the higher the dry matter content, the higher TSS content; and the higher the pH value, the lower the TTA.

Figure 5. Total ash content of berry fruits

Regarding total ash content blueberry had the lower ash content (0.31g/100g of sample f.w.) and blackberry had the higher content (0.71 g/100 g). Results were higher than those found by Moraes et al. (2007), and close to the study of Hirsch et al. (2012) and Françoso et al. (2008).

Figure 6. Vitamin C content in berry fruits

Vitamin C content resulted 10.6-48.8 mg/100 g of sample f.w., where strawberry was noted for higher content, and blueberry for the smallest, no significant differences existed among blackberry and raspberry.

Beside changes that occur during the maturation on physico-chemical parameters, depending on various factors such as light, temperature, moisture, and soil fertility among others, also their changes are important during postharvest handling of berry fruits, and to ensure the quality and marketing requirements (Gómez-Romero et al, 2010). Furthermore, the physico-chemical parameters are considered important as pre-processing parameters that can affect the quality of value-added berry products (Mitcham, 2007), and the obtained data provide significant information for berry consumers and processors for use and selection of appropriate

varieties for various applications. Based on requirements for the processing industry as suggested by Hokanson and Finn (2000), berry fruits would be excellent because of their high TSS and acid, deep red color, and relatively uniform size and shape.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study, physico-chemical parameters have differences among blueberry, blackberry, raspberry and strawberry in this study and when compared to other studies. Changes on physico-chemical parameters may have been affected by cultivar and maturation.

The berry fruits are small fruits with a weight per fruit 1.08-25.10 g, length 10.80-45.92 mm, width 13.03-35.38 mm and fruit shape index 0.83-1.3, among them blueberry is the smallest and strawberry the biggest. Color is a key parameter of post-harvest quality for red fruits, and the blueberry had the highest L* value (30.26), and the lowest blackberry (17.05), raspberry resulted with a higher positive value of a* (18.93) indicating that they are redder in the skin, and with a lower value resulted blueberry (1.58), and raspberry had the higher positive value b* (6.49), and with lower values resulted blueberry (-4.01).

From comparison between fruits blackberry resulted with the highest content of D.M., ash, pH, and with the lowest TTA, strawberry resulted with the highest vitamin C content and blueberry with the highest TSS. Variation were noted for TTA, TSS and vitamin C, whereas no significant differences were noted for other determined physico-chemical parameters.

The obtained data from this study on berry fruits provide significant information for postharvest handling of berry fruits, linked with their quality and marketing requirements assurance, as well as pre-processing parameters that can affect the quality of value-added berry products, and for use and selection of appropriate varieties for various applications.

Future studies may be focused on investigation of total polyphenol content and antioxidant potential of these fruits.

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